

SR&MA PICOS

Short version – See protocol for more elaborate

Population

- Adults (aged ≥ 18 years) with diagnosis of a dementia or diagnosis of mild cognitive impairment.
- Dementia diagnosis: DSM IV, DSM 5, ICD-10, alternative validated diagnostic criteria, or recorded in medical journal/confirmed by healthcare professional. Alzheimer's disease, vascular dementia, dementia with Lewy bodies and frontotemporal dementia all eligible for inclusion.
- Mild cognitive impairment diagnosis: DSM-5 criteria, Petersen's criteria (P-MCI), alternative validated diagnostic criteria, or recorded in medical journal/confirmed by healthcare professional.

No limitations will be placed on length of time since diagnosis and severity of dementia, severity of depression, anxiety, psychological distress or mental health-related quality of life. Dementia patients both in community and institutional settings are eligible.

Intervention

Any psychological therapy that uses specific therapeutic principles and techniques hypothesised to **target an improvement in psychological well-being or a reduction in symptoms** associated with psychological difficulties (**depression, anxiety, psychological distress, quality of life with a mental health-specific subscale, or psychological well-being**)

Psychological treatments of depression as defined by Cuijpers et al. (2020) with examples:

- Cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT)
Examples you might see:
 - CBT according to Beck's manual
 - "Coping with depression" Course
 - Guided self-help with the book "Feeling good" from David Burns
 - Some CBT techniques that might be used and described in paper
 - Goal-setting
 - Cognitive restructuring
 - Cognitive reframing
 - Behavioural experiment
 - Exposure (for anxiety)
- Behavioural activation therapy (BA)
Examples you might see:
 - Pleasant activity scheduling
 - Contextual behavioural activation
- Problem-solving therapy (PST)
Examples you might see:
 - Extended problem-solving therapy
 - Brief problem-solving therapy
 - Self-examination therapy (SET)
- Third wave cognitive behavioural therapies
Examples you might see:
 - Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT)

- Mindfulness-based CBT (MBCT)
- Interpersonal psychotherapy
 - Examples you might see:
 - Full IPT
 - Brief IPT
- Psychodynamic Therapy
- Non-directive supportive therapy
 - Examples you might see:
 - Counselling
 - Supportive therapy
- Life review therapy
 - Example you might see:
 - Reminiscence therapy (think about target, see above)

Examples of therapies that will be excluded: Cognitive stimulation therapy (CST), generally exclude studies targeting Behavioural and Psychological Symptoms of Dementia (BPSD), Medication, Exercise, Music therapy, Art and Drama therapy, Cognitive training, Cognitive rehabilitation, Psychoeducation (passive psychoeducation as defined by Donker et al., 2009).

Comparisons

- Active and inactive comparators eligible.
- Trial design must allow to isolate effect of the psychological intervention.
- Examples:
 - (1) Psychological intervention vs. control (no-treatment; wait-list; treatment as usual)
 - (2) Psychological intervention vs. non-specific factor component control
 - (3) Psychological intervention plus medication vs. medication
 - (4) Psychological intervention plus information vs. information

Outcome

- One or more of the following self-report, clinician or proxy administered **primary** outcome measurements for people with dementia:
 - (1) Standardised measurement of depression (e.g. BDI-II)
 - (2) Standardised measurement of anxiety (e.g. BAI)
 - (3) Standardised measurement of psychological distress (e.g. GHQ)
 - (4) Standardised measurement of quality of life **if they include** a mental health-specific subscale or domain (e.g. SF-36, ADRQL)
 - (5) Standardised measurement of psychological well-being (e.g. WEMWBS)
- Where multiple time points are reported, a primary end point ≤ 6 months post-treatment will be adopted.

Study design

- Randomised controlled trials (RCTs) and cluster RCTs.
- Quasi-RCTs and cross-over trials will not be eligible for inclusion.

Cuijpers, P., Karyotaki, E., de Wit, L., & Ebert, D. D. (2020). The effects of fifteen evidence-supported therapies for adult depression: A meta-analytic review. *Psychotherapy research*, 30(3), 279–293.

Donker, T., Griffiths, K.M., Cuijpers, P. et al. Psychoeducation for depression, anxiety and psychological distress: a meta-analysis. BMC Med 7, 79 (2009). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1741-7015-7-79>

Updates

2021-09-03: Well-being added to outcomes

2021-09-10: Added examples of CBT techniques that you might see in papers

Reminiscence developed to treat depression but might be used for quality of life as well. Reminiscence as intervention OK, but think about target and that outcomes are correct.

Clarification: Quality of life should have mental health-specific subscale or domain, should be clearly stated that mental health is included (e.g., SF-36)

2021-09-24: Target of intervention in bold, added ADQRL as QoL outcome example.

2025-02-06: Clarifying primary outcomes for people with dementia. Also extract outcome data for caregivers if included in paper

2025-02-11: EQ-5D / EQ-VAS is a global health and not mental health specific, therefore not included.